

THE FORM OF THE SOLUTIONS OF FOURTH ORDER RATIONAL SYSTEMS OF DIFFERENCE EQUATIONS

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ABSTRACT. In this paper, we get the form of the solutions of the following difference equation systems of order four

$$z_{n+1} = \frac{z_n w_{n-2}}{w_{n-2} + w_{n-3}}, \quad w_{n+1} = \frac{w_n z_{n-2}}{\pm z_{n-2} \pm z_{n-3}},$$

where the initial conditions $z_{-3}, z_{-2}, z_{-1}, z_0, w_{-3}, w_{-2}, w_{-1}, w_0$ are arbitrary non-zero real numbers.

1. INTRODUCTION

Our aim in this paper to get the solutions of the system of following rational difference equations

$$z_{n+1} = \frac{z_n w_{n-2}}{w_{n-2} + w_{n-3}}, \quad w_{n+1} = \frac{w_n z_{n-2}}{\pm z_{n-2} \pm z_{n-3}},$$

where the initial conditions $z_{-3}, z_{-2}, z_{-1}, z_0, w_{-3}, w_{-2}, w_{-1}, w_0$ are arbitrary non-zero real numbers. Recently, there has been a great interest in studying nonlinear difference equations and systems. One reason for this is the need for methods that may be used to investigate equations that arise in mathematical models reflecting real life situations in population biology, economics, probability theory, genetics, psychology, and sociology. Furthermore, most nonlinear differential equations can be approximated into difference relations or systems. We highlight the following studies among the numerous that already exist.

Theoretical and numerical solutions to the systems of rational difference equations were obtained by Almatrafi and Elsayed [2].

$$z_{n+1} = \frac{w_{n-1} z_{n-3}}{w_{n-1}(1 + w_{n-1} z_{n-3})}, \quad w_{n+1} = \frac{z_{n-1} w_{n-3}}{z_{n-1}(1 + z_{n-1} w_{n-3})}.$$

Clark et al. [4] has examined the global stability characteristics and asymptotic behavior of solutions of the system

$$z_{n+1} = \frac{z_n}{a + cw_n}, \quad w_{n+1} = \frac{w_n}{b + dz_n}.$$

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Cinar [5] has found the positive solution of the following systems of difference equations

$$z_{n+1} = \frac{1}{w_n}, \quad w_{n+1} = \frac{w_n}{z_{n-1}w_{n-1}}.$$

In [26] Kurbanli presented the behavior of solutions of the difference equation system

$$z_{n+1} = \frac{z_{n-1}}{w_n z_{n-1} - 1}, \quad w_{n+1} = \frac{w_{n-1}}{z_n w_{n-1} - 1}.$$

Touafek and Elsayed [33] studied the periodic nature and investigated specific solutions of the difference equation system presented below.

$$z_{n+1} = \frac{z_{n-3}}{\pm 1 \pm z_{n-3}w_{n-1}}, \quad w_{n+1} = \frac{w_{n-3}}{\pm 1 \pm w_{n-3}z_{n-1}}.$$

Yalcinkaya [36] investigated the sufficient condition for the global asymptotic stability of the following system of difference equations

$$z_{n+1} = \frac{w_n z_{n-1} + a}{w_n + z_{n-1}}, \quad w_{n+1} = \frac{z_n w_{n-1} + a}{z_n + w_{n-1}}.$$

Elsayed [15] discussed the periodic nature and found the solution of the difference equation

$$z_{n+1} = \frac{z_{n-3}w_{n-2}}{w_n(\pm 1 \pm z_{n-1}w_{n-2}z_{n-3})}, \quad w_{n+1} = \frac{z_{n-2}w_{n-3}}{z_n(\pm 1 \pm w_{n-1}z_{n-2}w_{n-3})}.$$

For more researches about the difference equations systems see refs. [1]- [40]. Now, we will obtain the form of the solutions of some systems of difference equations.

$$2. \text{ ON THE SYSTEM: } z_{n+1} = \frac{z_n w_{n-2}}{w_{n-2} + w_{n-3}}, \quad w_{n+1} = \frac{w_n z_{n-2}}{z_{n-2} + z_{n-3}}$$

In this section, we study the solutions of the following system of difference equations

$$z_{n+1} = \frac{z_n w_{n-2}}{w_{n-2} + w_{n-3}}, \quad w_{n+1} = \frac{w_n z_{n-2}}{z_{n-2} + z_{n-3}}, \quad (2.1)$$

where the initial conditions $z_{-3}, z_{-2}, z_{-1}, z_0, w_{-3}, w_{-2}, w_{-1}, w_0$ are arbitrary non-zero real numbers.

Theorem 1. Suppose that $\{z_n, w_n\}_{n=-3}^{\infty}$ are solutions of the system (2.1). Then for $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, we have the following formula

$$z_{6n-3} = \frac{d a^n h^n g^n f^n c^n b^n}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} [(2i+1)h+k][(2i+1)g+h][(2i+1)f+g][2ic+d][2ib+c][2ia+b]},$$

$$z_{6n-2} = \frac{a^n h^n g^n f^n c^{n+1} b^n}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} [(2i+1)h+k][(2i+1)g+h][(2i+1)f+g][2(i+1)c+d][2ib+c][2ia+b]},$$

$$z_{6n-1} = \frac{a^n h^n g^n f^n c^n b^{n+1}}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} [(2i+1)h+k][(2i+1)g+h][(2i+1)f+g][2(i+1)c+d][2(i+1)b+c][2ia+b]},$$

$$z_{6n} = \frac{a^{n+1} h^n g^n f^n c^n b^n}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} [(2i+1)h+k][(2i+1)g+h][(2i+1)f+g][2(i+1)c+d][2(i+1)b+c][2(i+1)a+b]},$$

$$z_{6n+1} = \frac{a^{n+1} h^{n+1} g^n f^n c^n b^n}{(h+k) \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} [(2i+3)h+k][(2i+1)g+h][(2i+1)f+g][2(i+1)c+d][2(i+1)b+c][2(i+1)a+b]},$$

$$z_{6n+2} = \frac{1}{(h+k)(g+h)} \times \frac{a^{n+1} h^{n+1} g^{n+1} f^n c^n b^n}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} [(2i+3)h+k][(2i+3)g+h][(2i+1)f+g][2(i+1)c+d][2(i+1)b+c][2(i+1)a+b]},$$

$$w_{6n-3} = \frac{k f^n c^n b^n a^n h^n g^n}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} [(2i+1)c+d][(2i+1)b+c][(2i+1)a+b][2ih+k][2ig+h][2if+g]},$$

$$w_{6n-2} = \frac{f^n c^n b^n a^n h^{n+1} g^n}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} [(2i+1)c+d][(2i+1)b+c][(2i+1)a+b][2(i+1)h+k][2ig+h][2if+g]},$$

$$w_{6n-1} = \frac{f^n c^n b^n a^n h^n g^{n+1}}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} [(2i+1)c+d][(2i+1)b+c][(2i+1)a+b][2(i+1)h+k][2(i+1)g+h][2if+g]},$$

$$w_{6n} = \frac{f^{n+1} c^n b^n a^n h^n g^n}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} [(2i+1)c+d][(2i+1)b+c][(2i+1)a+b][2(i+1)h+k][2(i+1)g+h][2(i+1)f+g]},$$

$$w_{6n+1} = \frac{f^{n+1} c^{n+1} b^n a^n h^n g^n}{(c+d) \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} [(2i+3)c+d][(2i+1)b+c][(2i+1)a+b][2(i+1)h+k][2(i+1)g+h][2(i+1)f+g]},$$

$$w_{6n+2} = \frac{1}{(c+d)(b+c)} \times \frac{f^{n+1} c^{n+1} b^{n+1} a^n h^n g^n}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} [(2i+3)c+d][(2i+3)b+c][(2i+1)a+b][2(i+1)h+k][2(i+1)g+h][2(i+1)f+g]},$$

where $z_{-3} = d$, $z_{-2} = c$, $z_{-1} = b$, $z_0 = a$, $w_{-3} = k$, $w_{-2} = h$, $w_{-1} = g$, $w_0 = f$.

Proof. By using mathematical induction. The result holds for $n = 0$. Suppose that the result holds for $n - 1$

$$z_{6n-9} = \frac{d a^{n-1} h^{n-1} g^{n-1} f^{n-1} c^{n-1} b^{n-1}}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-2} [(2i+1)h+k][(2i+1)g+h][(2i+1)f+g][2ic+d][2ib+c][2ia+b]},$$

$$\begin{aligned}
z_{6n-8} &= \frac{a^{n-1} h^{n-1} g^{n-1} f^{n-1} c^n b^{n-1}}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-2} [(2i+1)h+k][(2i+1)g+h][(2i+1)f+g][2(i+1)c+d][2ib+c][2ia+b]}, \\
z_{6n-7} &= \frac{a^{n-1} h^{n-1} g^{n-1} f^{n-1} c^{n-1} b^n}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-2} [(2i+1)h+k][(2i+1)g+h][(2i+1)f+g][2(i+1)c+d][2(i+1)b+c][2ia+b]}, \\
z_{6n-6} &= \frac{a^n h^{n-1} g^{n-1} f^{n-1} c^{n-1} b^{n-1}}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-2} [(2i+1)h+k][(2i+1)g+h][(2i+1)f+g][2(i+1)c+d][2(i+1)b+c][2(i+1)a+b]}, \\
z_{6n-5} &= \frac{a^n h^n g^{n-1} f^{n-1} c^{n-1} b^{n-1}}{(h+k) \prod_{i=0}^{n-2} [(2i+3)h+k][(2i+1)g+h][(2i+1)f+g][2(i+1)c+d][2(i+1)b+c][2(i+1)a+b]}, \\
z_{6n-4} &= \frac{a^n h^n g^n f^{n-1} c^{n-1} b^{n-1}}{(h+k)(g+h) \prod_{i=0}^{n-2} [(2i+3)h+k][(2i+3)g+h][(2i+1)f+g][2(i+1)c+d][2(i+1)b+c][2(i+1)a+b]}, \\
w_{6n-9} &= \frac{k f^{n-1} c^{n-1} b^{n-1} a^{n-1} h^{n-1} g^{n-1}}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-2} [(2i+1)c+d][(2i+1)b+c][(2i+1)a+b][2ih+k][2ig+h][2if+g]}, \\
w_{6n-8} &= \frac{f^{n-1} c^{n-1} b^{n-1} a^{n-1} h^n g^{n-1}}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-2} [(2i+1)c+d][(2i+1)b+c][(2i+1)a+b][2(i+1)h+k][2ig+h][2if+g]}, \\
w_{6n-7} &= \frac{f^{n-1} c^{n-1} b^{n-1} a^{n-1} h^{n-1} g^n}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-2} [(2i+1)c+d][(2i+1)b+c][(2i+1)a+b][2(i+1)h+k][2(i+1)g+h][2if+g]}, \\
w_{6n-6} &= \frac{f^n c^{n-1} b^{n-1} a^{n-1} h^{n-1} g^{n-1}}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-2} [(2i+1)c+d][(2i+1)b+c][(2i+1)a+b][2(i+1)h+k][2(i+1)g+h][2(i+1)f+g]}, \\
w_{6n-5} &= \frac{f^n c^n b^{n-1} a^{n-1} h^{n-1} g^{n-1}}{(c+d) \prod_{i=0}^{n-2} [(2i+3)c+d][(2i+1)b+c][(2i+1)a+b][2(i+1)h+k][2(i+1)g+h][2(i+1)f+g]}, \\
w_{6n-4} &= \frac{f^n c^n b^n a^{n-1} h^{n-1} g^{n-1}}{(c+d)(b+c) \prod_{i=0}^{n-2} [(2i+3)c+d][(2i+3)b+c][(2i+1)a+b][2(i+1)h+k][2(i+1)g+h][2(i+1)f+g]}.
\end{aligned}$$

From system (2.1) we can prove as follow but firstly, to prove z_{6n-3} we found the following relation

$$\begin{aligned}
w_{6n-6} &= \frac{f w_{6n-7}}{(2n-2)f+g}, \\
\Leftrightarrow w_{6n-7} &= \frac{[(2n-2)f+g]w_{6n-6}}{f}.
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned}
z_{6n-3} &= \frac{z_{6n-4}w_{6n-6}}{w_{6n-6} + w_{6n-7}} \\
&= \frac{z_{6n-4}w_{6n-6}}{w_{6n-6} + \frac{[(2n-2)f+g]w_{6n-6}}{f}} \\
&= \frac{f z_{6n-4}}{(2n-1)f + g} \\
&= \frac{f}{(2n-1)f + g} \cdot \frac{a^n h^n g^n f^{n-1} c^{n-1} b^{n-1}}{(h+k)(g+h) \prod_{i=0}^{n-2} [(2i+3)h+k][(2i+3)g+h][(2i+1)f+g] \\
&\quad [2(i+1)c+d][2(i+1)b+c][2(i+1)a+b]} \\
&= \frac{f}{(2n-1)f + g} \cdot \frac{d c b a^n h^n g^n f^{n-1} c^{n-1} b^{n-1}}{(h+k)(g+h) \prod_{i=0}^{n-2} [(2i+3)h+k][(2i+3)g+h][(2i+1)f+g] \\
&\quad [2(i+1)c+d]c[2(i+1)b+c]b[2(i+1)a+b]} \\
&= \frac{f}{(2n-1)f + g} \cdot \frac{d a^n h^n g^n f^n c^n b^n}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} [(2i+1)h+k][(2i+1)g+h][(2i+1)f+g][2ic+d][2ib+c][2ia+b]},
\end{aligned}$$

to prove w_{6n-3} we found the following relation

$$\begin{aligned}
z_{6n-6} &= \frac{az_{6n-7}}{(2n-2)a + b}, \\
\Leftrightarrow z_{6n-7} &= \frac{[(2n-2)a + b]z_{6n-6}}{a}.
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned}
w_{6n-3} &= \frac{w_{6n-4}z_{6n-6}}{z_{6n-6} + z_{6n-7}} \\
&= \frac{w_{6n-4}z_{6n-6}}{z_{6n-6} + \frac{[(2n-2)a+b]z_{6n-6}}{a}} \\
&= \frac{aw_{6n-4}}{(2n-1)a + b} \\
&= \frac{a}{(2n-1)a + b} \cdot \frac{f^n c^n b^n a^{n-1} h^{n-1} g^{n-1}}{(c+d)(b+c) \prod_{i=0}^{n-2} [(2i+3)c+d][(2i+3)b+c][(2i+1)a+b] \\
&\quad [2(i+1)h+k][2(i+1)g+h][2(i+1)f+g]} \\
&= \frac{a}{(2n-1)a + b} \cdot \frac{k h g f^n c^n b^n a^{n-1} h^{n-1} g^{n-1}}{(c+d)(b+c) \prod_{i=0}^{n-2} [(2i+3)c+d][(2i+3)b+c][(2i+1)a+b]k \\
&\quad [2(i+1)h+k]h[2(i+1)g+h]g[2(i+1)f+g]} \\
&= \frac{a}{(2n-1)a + b} \cdot \frac{k f^n c^n b^n a^n h^n g^n}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} [(2i+1)c+d][(2i+1)b+c][(2i+1)a+b][2ih+k][2ig+h][2if+g]}.
\end{aligned}$$

Similarly we can prove other relations and the proof is completed. $\square$

$$3. \text{ ON THE SYSTEM: } z_{n+1} = \frac{z_n w_{n-2}}{w_{n-2} + w_{n-3}}, \quad w_{n+1} = \frac{w_n z_{n-2}}{z_{n-2} - z_{n-3}}$$

We study in this section the solutions of the system of two difference equations

$$z_{n+1} = \frac{z_n w_{n-2}}{w_{n-2} + w_{n-3}}, \quad w_{n+1} = \frac{w_n z_{n-2}}{z_{n-2} - z_{n-3}}, \quad (3.1)$$

where the initial conditions $z_{-3}, z_{-2}, z_{-1}, z_0, w_{-3}, w_{-2}, w_{-1}, w_0$ are arbitrary non-zero real numbers.

Theorem 2. Assume that $\{z_n, w_n\}_{n=-3}^{\infty}$ is a solution to system (3.1) and let $z_{-3} = d, z_{-2} = c, z_{-1} = b, z_0 = a, w_{-3} = k, w_{-2} = h, w_{-1} = g$ and $w_0 = f$ with $w_{-2} \neq \pm w_{-3}, w_{-1} \neq \pm w_{-2}, w_0 \neq \pm w_{-1}, z_{-2} \neq \pm z_{-3}, z_{-1} \neq \pm z_{-2}$ and $z_0 \neq \pm z_{-1}$. Then, for $n = 0, 1, \dots$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} z_{12n-3} &= \frac{a^{2n} h^{2n} g^{2n} f^{2n} c^n b^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^n (h-k)^n (g-h)^n (f-g)^n d^{n-1}}, \\ z_{12n-2} &= \frac{a^{2n} h^{2n} g^{2n} f^{2n} c^{n+1} b^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^n (h-k)^n (g-h)^n (f-g)^n d^n}, \\ z_{12n-1} &= \frac{a^{2n} h^{2n} g^{2n} f^{2n} c^n b^{n+1}}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^n (h-k)^n (g-h)^n (f-g)^n d^n}, \\ z_{12n} &= \frac{a^{2n+1} h^{2n} g^{2n} f^{2n} c^n b^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^n (h-k)^n (g-h)^n (f-g)^n d^n}, \\ z_{12n+1} &= \frac{a^{2n+1} h^{2n+1} g^{2n} f^{2n} c^n b^n}{(h+k)^{n+1} (g+h)^n (f+g)^n (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^n (h-k)^n (g-h)^n (f-g)^n d^n}, \\ z_{12n+2} &= \frac{a^{2n+1} h^{2n+1} g^{2n+1} f^{2n} c^n b^n}{(h+k)^{n+1} (g+h)^{n+1} (f+g)^n (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^n (h-k)^n (g-h)^n (f-g)^n d^n}, \\ z_{12n+3} &= \frac{a^{2n+1} h^{2n+1} g^{2n+1} f^{2n+1} c^n b^n}{(h+k)^{n+1} (g+h)^{n+1} (f+g)^{n+1} (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^n (h-k)^n (g-h)^n (f-g)^n d^n}, \\ z_{12n+4} &= \frac{a^{2n+1} h^{2n+1} g^{2n+1} f^{2n+1} c^{n+1} b^n}{(h+k)^{n+1} (g+h)^{n+1} (f+g)^{n+1} (2c-d)^{n+1} (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^n (h-k)^n (g-h)^n (f-g)^n d^n}, \\ z_{12n+5} &= \frac{a^{2n+1} h^{2n+1} g^{2n+1} f^{2n+1} c^{n+1} b^{n+1}}{(h+k)^{n+1} (g+h)^{n+1} (f+g)^{n+1} (2c-d)^{n+1} (2b-c)^{n+1} (2a-b)^n (h-k)^n (g-h)^n (f-g)^n d^n}, \\ z_{12n+6} &= \frac{a^{2n+2} h^{2n+1} g^{2n+1} f^{2n+1} c^{n+1} b^{n+1}}{(h+k)^{n+1} (g+h)^{n+1} (f+g)^{n+1} (2c-d)^{n+1} (2b-c)^{n+1} (2a-b)^{n+1} (h-k)^n (g-h)^n (f-g)^n d^n}, \\ z_{12n+7} &= \frac{a^{2n+2} h^{2n+2} g^{2n+1} f^{2n+1} c^{n+1} b^{n+1}}{(h+k)^{n+1} (g+h)^{n+1} (f+g)^{n+1} (2c-d)^{n+1} (2b-c)^{n+1} (2a-b)^{n+1} (h-k)^{n+1} (g-h)^n (f-g)^n d^n}, \\ z_{12n+8} &= \frac{a^{2n+2} h^{2n+2} g^{2n+2} f^{2n+1} c^{n+1} b^{n+1}}{(h+k)^{n+1} (g+h)^{n+1} (f+g)^{n+1} (2c-d)^{n+1} (2b-c)^{n+1} (2a-b)^{n+1} (h-k)^{n+1} (g-h)^{n+1} (f-g)^n d^n}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
w_{12n-3} &= \frac{f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n} a^{2n}}{(c-d)^{2n}(b-c)^{2n}(a-b)^{2n} k^{2n-1}}, & w_{12n-2} &= \frac{f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n} a^{2n} h}{(c-d)^{2n}(b-c)^{2n}(a-b)^{2n} k^{2n}}, \\
w_{12n-1} &= \frac{f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n} a^{2n} g}{(c-d)^{2n}(b-c)^{2n}(a-b)^{2n} k^{2n}}, & w_{12n} &= \frac{f^{2n+1} c^{2n} b^{2n} a^{2n}}{(c-d)^{2n}(b-c)^{2n}(a-b)^{2n} k^{2n}}, \\
w_{12n+1} &= \frac{f^{2n+1} c^{2n+1} b^{2n} a^{2n}}{(c-d)^{2n+1}(b-c)^{2n}(a-b)^{2n} k^{2n}}, & w_{12n+2} &= \frac{f^{2n+1} c^{2n+1} b^{2n+1} a^{2n}}{(c-d)^{2n+1}(b-c)^{2n+1}(a-b)^{2n} k^{2n}}, \\
w_{12n+3} &= \frac{f^{2n+1} c^{2n+1} b^{2n+1} a^{2n+1}}{(c-d)^{2n+1}(b-c)^{2n+1}(a-b)^{2n+1} k^{2n}}, & w_{12n+4} &= \frac{-f^{2n+1} c^{2n+1} b^{2n+1} a^{2n+1} h}{(c-d)^{2n+1}(b-c)^{2n+1}(a-b)^{2n+1} k^{2n+1}}, \\
w_{12n+5} &= \frac{f^{2n+1} c^{2n+1} b^{2n+1} a^{2n+1} g}{(c-d)^{2n+1}(b-c)^{2n+1}(a-b)^{2n+1} k^{2n+1}}, & w_{12n+6} &= \frac{-f^{2n+2} c^{2n+1} b^{2n+1} a^{2n+1}}{(c-d)^{2n+1}(b-c)^{2n+1}(a-b)^{2n+1} k^{2n+1}}, \\
w_{12n+7} &= \frac{f^{2n+2} c^{2n+2} b^{2n+1} a^{2n+1}}{(c-d)^{2n+2}(b-c)^{2n+1}(a-b)^{2n+1} k^{2n+1}}, & w_{12n+8} &= \frac{-f^{2n+2} c^{2n+2} b^{2n+2} a^{2n+1}}{(c-d)^{2n+2}(b-c)^{2n+2}(a-b)^{2n+1} k^{2n+1}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. For $n = 0$ the result holds. Now suppose that $n > 0$ and that our assumption holds for $n - 1$. That is,

$$\begin{aligned}
z_{12n-15} &= \frac{a^{2n-2} h^{2n-2} g^{2n-2} f^{2n-2} c^{n-1} b^{n-1}}{(h+k)^{n-1}(g+h)^{n-1}(f+g)^{n-1}(2c-d)^{n-1}(2b-c)^{n-1}(2a-b)^{n-1}(h-k)^{n-1} (g-h)^{n-1}(f-g)^{n-1} d^{n-2}}, \\
z_{12n-14} &= \frac{a^{2n-2} h^{2n-2} g^{2n-2} f^{2n-2} c^n b^{n-1}}{(h+k)^{n-1}(g+h)^{n-1}(f+g)^{n-1}(2c-d)^{n-1}(2b-c)^{n-1}(2a-b)^{n-1}(h-k)^{n-1} (g-h)^{n-1}(f-g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}, \\
z_{12n-13} &= \frac{a^{2n-2} h^{2n-2} g^{2n-2} f^{2n-2} c^{n-1} b^n}{(h+k)^{n-1}(g+h)^{n-1}(f+g)^{n-1}(2c-d)^{n-1}(2b-c)^{n-1}(2a-b)^{n-1}(h-k)^{n-1} (g-h)^{n-1}(f-g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}, \\
z_{12n-12} &= \frac{a^{2n-1} h^{2n-2} g^{2n-2} f^{2n-2} c^{n-1} b^{n-1}}{(h+k)^{n-1}(g+h)^{n-1}(f+g)^{n-1}(2c-d)^{n-1}(2b-c)^{n-1}(2a-b)^{n-1}(h-k)^{n-1} (g-h)^{n-1}(f-g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}, \\
z_{12n-11} &= \frac{a^{2n-1} h^{2n-1} g^{2n-2} f^{2n-2} c^{n-1} b^{n-1}}{(h+k)^n(g+h)^{n-1}(f+g)^{n-1}(2c-d)^{n-1}(2b-c)^{n-1}(2a-b)^{n-1}(h-k)^{n-1} (g-h)^{n-1}(f-g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}, \\
z_{12n-10} &= \frac{a^{2n-1} h^{2n-1} g^{2n-1} f^{2n-2} c^{n-1} b^{n-1}}{(h+k)^n(g+h)^n(f+g)^{n-1}(2c-d)^{n-1}(2b-c)^{n-1}(2a-b)^{n-1}(h-k)^{n-1} (g-h)^{n-1}(f-g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}, \\
z_{12n-9} &= \frac{a^{2n-1} h^{2n-1} g^{2n-1} f^{2n-1} c^{n-1} b^{n-1}}{(h+k)^n(g+h)^n(f+g)^n(2c-d)^{n-1}(2b-c)^{n-1}(2a-b)^{n-1}(h-k)^{n-1}(g-h)^{n-1}(f-g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}, \\
z_{12n-8} &= \frac{a^{2n-1} h^{2n-1} g^{2n-1} f^{2n-1} c^n b^{n-1}}{(h+k)^n(g+h)^n(f+g)^n(2c-d)^n(2b-c)^{n-1}(2a-b)^{n-1}(h-k)^{n-1}(g-h)^{n-1}(f-g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}},
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
z_{12n-7} &= \frac{a^{2n-1} h^{2n-1} g^{2n-1} f^{2n-1} c^n b^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^{n-1} (h-k)^{n-1} (g-h)^{n-1} (f-g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}, \\
z_{12n-6} &= \frac{a^{2n} h^{2n-1} g^{2n-1} f^{2n-1} c^n b^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^n (h-k)^{n-1} (g-h)^{n-1} (f-g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}, \\
z_{12n-5} &= \frac{a^{2n} h^{2n} g^{2n-1} f^{2n-1} c^n b^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^n (h-k)^n (g-h)^{n-1} (f-g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}, \\
z_{12n-4} &= \frac{a^{2n} h^{2n} g^{2n} f^{2n-1} c^n b^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^n (h-k)^n (g-h)^n (f-g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}, \\
w_{12n-15} &= \frac{f^{2n-2} c^{2n-2} b^{2n-2} a^{2n-2}}{(c-d)^{2n-2} (b-c)^{2n-2} (a-b)^{2n-2} k^{2n-3}}, \\
w_{12n-14} &= \frac{f^{2n-2} c^{2n-2} b^{2n-2} a^{2n-2} h}{(c-d)^{2n-2} (b-c)^{2n-2} (a-b)^{2n-2} k^{2n-2}}, \\
w_{12n-13} &= \frac{f^{2n-2} c^{2n-2} b^{2n-2} a^{2n-2} g}{(c-d)^{2n-2} (b-c)^{2n-2} (a-b)^{2n-2} k^{2n-2}}, \\
w_{12n-12} &= \frac{f^{2n-1} c^{2n-2} b^{2n-2} a^{2n-2}}{(c-d)^{2n-2} (b-c)^{2n-2} (a-b)^{2n-2} k^{2n-2}}, \\
w_{12n-11} &= \frac{f^{2n-1} c^{2n-1} b^{2n-2} a^{2n-2}}{(c-d)^{2n-1} (b-c)^{2n-2} (a-b)^{2n-2} k^{2n-2}}, \\
w_{12n-10} &= \frac{f^{2n-1} c^{2n-1} b^{2n-1} a^{2n-2}}{(c-d)^{2n-1} (b-c)^{2n-1} (a-b)^{2n-2} k^{2n-2}}, \\
w_{12n-9} &= \frac{f^{2n-1} c^{2n-1} b^{2n-1} a^{2n-1}}{(c-d)^{2n-1} (b-c)^{2n-1} (a-b)^{2n-1} k^{2n-2}}, \\
w_{12n-8} &= \frac{f^{2n-1} c^{2n-1} b^{2n-1} a^{2n-1} h}{(c-d)^{2n-1} (b-c)^{2n-1} (a-b)^{2n-1} k^{2n-1}}, \\
w_{12n-7} &= \frac{f^{2n-1} c^{2n-1} b^{2n-1} a^{2n-1} g}{(c-d)^{2n-1} (b-c)^{2n-1} (a-b)^{2n-1} k^{2n-1}}, \\
w_{12n-6} &= \frac{f^{2n} c^{2n-1} b^{2n-1} a^{2n-1}}{(c-d)^{2n-1} (b-c)^{2n-1} (a-b)^{2n-1} k^{2n-1}}, \\
w_{12n-5} &= \frac{f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n-1} a^{2n-1}}{(c-d)^{2n} (b-c)^{2n-1} (a-b)^{2n-1} k^{2n-1}}, \\
w_{12n-4} &= \frac{f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n} a^{2n-1}}{(c-d)^{2n} (b-c)^{2n} (a-b)^{2n-1} k^{2n-1}}.
\end{aligned}$$

From system (3.1) we can prove as follow

$$\begin{aligned}
z_{12n-3} &= \frac{z_{12n-4} w_{12n-6}}{w_{12n-6} + w_{12n-7}} \\
&= \frac{\frac{a^{2n} h^{2n} g^{2n} f^{2n-1} c^n b^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^n (h-k)^n (g-h)^n (f-g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}}{\frac{-f^{2n} c^{2n-1} b^{2n-1} a^{2n-1}}{(c-d)^{2n-1} (b-c)^{2n-1} (a-b)^{2n-1} k^{2n-1}} + \frac{f^{2n-1} c^{2n-1} b^{2n-1} a^{2n-1} g}{(c-d)^{2n-1} (b-c)^{2n-1} (a-b)^{2n-1} k^{2n-1}}} \\
&= \frac{-a^{2n} h^{2n} g^{2n} f^{2n-1} c^n b^n f}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^n (h-k)^n (g-h)^n (f-g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}} \\
&= \frac{-f + g}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^n (h-k)^n (g-h)^n (f-g)^n d^{n-1}},
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
z_{12n-2} &= \frac{z_{12n-3}w_{12n-5}}{w_{12n-5} + w_{12n-6}} \\
&= \frac{\left(\frac{a^{2n} h^{2n} g^{2n} f^{2n} c^n b^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^n (h-k)^n (g-h)^n (f-g)^n d^{n-1}} \right)}{\left(\frac{f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n-1} a^{2n-1}}{(c-d)^{2n} (b-c)^{2n-1} (a-b)^{2n-1} k^{2n-1}} \right)} \\
&= \frac{\left(\frac{f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n-1} a^{2n-1}}{(c-d)^{2n} (b-c)^{2n-1} (a-b)^{2n-1} k^{2n-1}} \right) + \left(\frac{-f^{2n} c^{2n-1} b^{2n-1} a^{2n-1}}{(c-d)^{2n-1} (b-c)^{2n-1} (a-b)^{2n-1} k^{2n-1}} \right)}{\left(\frac{a^{2n} h^{2n} g^{2n} f^{2n} c^{n+1} b^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^n (h-k)^n (g-h)^n (f-g)^n d^{n-1} (c-d)} \right)} \\
&= \frac{\frac{c}{c-d} - 1}{a^{2n} h^{2n} g^{2n} f^{2n} c^{n+1} b^n} \\
&= \frac{1}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^n (h-k)^n (g-h)^n (f-g)^n d^n}, \\
w_{12n-3} &= \frac{w_{12n-4}z_{12n-6}}{z_{12n-6} - z_{12n-7}} \\
&= \frac{\left(\frac{-f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n} a^{2n-1}}{(c-d)^{2n} (b-c)^{2n} (a-b)^{2n-1} k^{2n-1}} \right)}{\left(\frac{a^{2n} h^{2n-1} g^{2n-1} f^{2n-1} c^n b^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^n (h-k)^{n-1} (g-h)^{n-1} (f-g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}} \right)} \\
&= \frac{\frac{a^{2n} h^{2n-1} g^{2n-1} f^{2n-1} c^n b^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^n (h-k)^{n-1} (g-h)^{n-1} (f-g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}} - \frac{a^{2n-1} h^{2n-1} g^{2n-1} f^{2n-1} c^n b^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^{n-1} (h-k)^{n-1} (g-h)^{n-1} (f-g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}}{\frac{-f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n} a^{2n}}{(c-d)^{2n} (b-c)^{2n} (a-b)^{2n-1} k^{2n-1} (2a-b)}} \\
&= \frac{\frac{a}{2a-b} - 1}{f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n} a^{2n}} \\
&= \frac{1}{(c-d)^{2n} (b-c)^{2n} (a-b)^{2n} k^{2n-1}}, \\
w_{12n-2} &= \frac{w_{12n-3}z_{12n-5}}{z_{12n-5} - z_{12n-6}} \\
&= \frac{\left(\frac{f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n} a^{2n}}{(c-d)^{2n} (b-c)^{2n} (a-b)^{2n} k^{2n-1}} \right)}{\left(\frac{a^{2n} h^{2n} g^{2n-1} f^{2n-1} c^n b^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^n (h-k)^n (g-h)^{n-1} (f-g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}} \right)} \\
&= \frac{\frac{a^{2n} h^{2n} g^{2n-1} f^{2n-1} c^n b^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^n (h-k)^n (g-h)^{n-1} (f-g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}} - \frac{a^{2n-1} h^{2n-1} g^{2n-1} f^{2n-1} c^n b^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n (2c-d)^n (2b-c)^n (2a-b)^n (h-k)^{n-1} (g-h)^{n-1} (f-g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}}{\frac{f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n} a^{2n} h}{(c-d)^{2n} (b-c)^{2n} (a-b)^{2n} k^{2n-1} (h-k)}} \\
&= \frac{\frac{h}{h-k} - 1}{f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n} a^{2n} h} \\
&= \frac{1}{(c-d)^{2n} (b-c)^{2n} (a-b)^{2n} k^{2n}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Similarly we can prove other relations and the proof is completed. $\square$

$$4. \text{ ON THE SYSTEM: } z_{n+1} = \frac{z_n w_{n-2}}{w_{n-2} + w_{n-3}}, \quad w_{n+1} = \frac{w_n z_{n-2}}{-z_{n-2} + z_{n-3}}$$

In this section, we deal with the solutions of the system of the difference equations

$$z_{n+1} = \frac{z_n w_{n-2}}{w_{n-2} + w_{n-3}}, \quad w_{n+1} = \frac{w_n z_{n-2}}{-z_{n-2} + z_{n-3}}, \quad (4.1)$$

where the initial conditions $z_{-3}, z_{-2}, z_{-1}, z_0, w_{-3}, w_{-2}, w_{-1}, w_0$ are arbitrary non-zero real numbers.

Theorem 3. Suppose that $\{z_n, w_n\}_{n=-3}^{\infty}$ are solutions of system (4.1). Then for $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$,

$$\begin{aligned} z_{6n-3} &= \frac{a^n h^n g^n f^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n d^{n-1}}, & z_{6n-2} &= \frac{c a^n h^n g^n f^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n d^n}, \\ z_{6n-1} &= \frac{b a^n h^n g^n f^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n d^n}, & z_{6n} &= \frac{a^{n+1} h^n g^n f^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n d^n}, \\ z_{6n+1} &= \frac{a^{n+1} h^{n+1} g^n f^n}{(h+k)^{n+1} (g+h)^n (f+g)^n d^n}, & z_{6n+2} &= \frac{a^{n+1} h^{n+1} g^{n+1} f^n}{(h+k)^{n+1} (g+h)^{n+1} (f+g)^n d^n}, \\ w_{6n-3} &= \frac{f^n c^n b^n a^n}{(-c+d)^n (-b+c)^n (-a+b)^n k^{n-1}}, & w_{6n-2} &= \frac{h f^n c^n b^n a^n}{(-c+d)^n (-b+c)^n (-a+b)^n k^n}, \\ w_{6n-1} &= \frac{g f^n c^n b^n a^n}{(-c+d)^n (-b+c)^n (-a+b)^n k^n}, & w_{6n} &= \frac{f^{n+1} c^n b^n a^n}{(-c+d)^n (-b+c)^n (-a+b)^n k^n}, \\ w_{6n+1} &= \frac{f^{n+1} c^{n+1} b^n a^n}{(-c+d)^{n+1} (-b+c)^n (-a+b)^n k^n}, & w_{6n+2} &= \frac{f^{n+1} c^{n+1} b^{n+1} a^n}{(-c+d)^{n+1} (-b+c)^{n+1} (-a+b)^n k^n}, \end{aligned}$$

where $z_{-3} = d, z_{-2} = c, z_{-1} = b, z_0 = a, w_{-3} = k, w_{-2} = h, w_{-1} = g$ and $w_0 = f$ with $w_{-2} \neq \pm w_{-3}, w_{-1} \neq \pm w_{-2}, w_0 \neq \pm w_{-1}, z_{-2} \neq \pm z_{-3}, z_{-1} \neq \pm z_{-2}$ and $z_0 \neq \pm z_{-1}$.

Proof. By using mathematical induction. The result holds for $n = 0$. Suppose that the result holds for $n - 1$

$$\begin{aligned} z_{6n-9} &= \frac{a^{n-1} h^{n-1} g^{n-1} f^{n-1}}{(h+k)^{n-1} (g+h)^{n-1} (f+g)^{n-1} d^{n-2}}, & z_{6n-8} &= \frac{c a^{n-1} h^{n-1} g^{n-1} f^{n-1}}{(h+k)^{n-1} (g+h)^{n-1} (f+g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}, \\ z_{6n-7} &= \frac{b a^{n-1} h^{n-1} g^{n-1} f^{n-1}}{(h+k)^{n-1} (g+h)^{n-1} (f+g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}, & z_{6n-6} &= \frac{a^n h^{n-1} g^{n-1} f^{n-1}}{(h+k)^{n-1} (g+h)^{n-1} (f+g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}, \\ z_{6n-5} &= \frac{a^n h^n g^{n-1} f^{n-1}}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^{n-1} (f+g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}, & z_{6n-4} &= \frac{a^n h^n g^n f^{n-1}}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}, \\ w_{6n-9} &= \frac{f^{n-1} c^{n-1} b^{n-1} a^{n-1}}{(-c+d)^{n-1} (-b+c)^{n-1} (-a+b)^{n-1} k^{n-2}}, & w_{6n-8} &= \frac{h f^{n-1} c^{n-1} b^{n-1} a^{n-1}}{(-c+d)^{n-1} (-b+c)^{n-1} (-a+b)^{n-1} k^{n-1}}, \\ w_{6n-7} &= \frac{g f^{n-1} c^{n-1} b^{n-1} a^{n-1}}{(-c+d)^{n-1} (-b+c)^{n-1} (-a+b)^{n-1} k^{n-1}}, & w_{6n-6} &= \frac{f^n c^{n-1} b^{n-1} a^{n-1}}{(-c+d)^{n-1} (-b+c)^{n-1} (-a+b)^{n-1} k^{n-1}}, \\ w_{6n-5} &= \frac{f^n c^n b^{n-1} a^{n-1}}{(-c+d)^n (-b+c)^{n-1} (-a+b)^{n-1} k^{n-1}}, & w_{6n-4} &= \frac{f^n c^n b^n a^{n-1}}{(-c+d)^n (-b+c)^n (-a+b)^{n-1} k^{n-1}}. \end{aligned}$$

From system (4.1) we can prove as follow

$$\begin{aligned}
z_{6n-3} &= \frac{z_{6n-4}w_{6n-6}}{w_{6n-6} + w_{6n-7}} \\
&= \frac{\frac{a^n h^n g^n f^{n-1}}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}} \times \frac{f^n c^{n-1} b^{n-1} a^{n-1}}{(-c+d)^{n-1} (-b+c)^{n-1} (-a+b)^{n-1} k^{n-1}}}{\frac{f^n c^{n-1} b^{n-1} a^{n-1}}{(-c+d)^{n-1} (-b+c)^{n-1} (-a+b)^{n-1} k^{n-1}} + \frac{g f^{n-1} c^{n-1} b^{n-1} a^{n-1}}{(-c+d)^{n-1} (-b+c)^{n-1} (-a+b)^{n-1} k^{n-1}}} \\
&= \frac{\frac{a^n h^n g^n f^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}}{\frac{f+g}{a^n h^n g^n f^n}} \\
&= \frac{a^n h^n g^n f^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n d^{n-1}}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
z_{6n-2} &= \frac{z_{6n-3}w_{6n-5}}{w_{6n-5} + w_{6n-6}} \\
&= \frac{\frac{a^n h^n g^n f^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n d^{n-1}} \times \frac{f^n c^n b^{n-1} a^{n-1}}{(-c+d)^n (-b+c)^{n-1} (-a+b)^{n-1} k^{n-1}}}{\frac{f^n c^n b^{n-1} a^{n-1}}{(-c+d)^n (-b+c)^{n-1} (-a+b)^{n-1} k^{n-1}} + \frac{f^n c^{n-1} b^{n-1} a^{n-1}}{(-c+d)^{n-1} (-b+c)^{n-1} (-a+b)^{n-1} k^{n-1}}} \\
&= \frac{\frac{c a^n h^n g^n f^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n d^{n-1} (-c+d)}}{\frac{c}{(-c+d)} + 1} \\
&= \frac{c a^n h^n g^n f^n}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^n (f+g)^n d^n}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
w_{6n-3} &= \frac{w_{6n-4}z_{6n-6}}{-z_{6n-6} + z_{6n-7}} \\
&= \frac{\frac{f^n c^n b^n a^{n-1}}{(-c+d)^n (-b+c)^n (-a+b)^{n-1} k^{n-1}} \times \frac{a^n h^{n-1} g^{n-1} f^{n-1}}{(h+k)^{n-1} (g+h)^{n-1} (f+g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}}{\frac{a^n h^{n-1} g^{n-1} f^{n-1}}{(h+k)^{n-1} (g+h)^{n-1} (f+g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}} + \frac{b a^{n-1} h^{n-1} g^{n-1} f^{n-1}}{(h+k)^{n-1} (g+h)^{n-1} (f+g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}} \\
&= \frac{\frac{f^n c^n b^n a^{n-1} a}{(-c+d)^n (-b+c)^n (-a+b)^{n-1} k^{n-1}}}{(-a+b)} \\
&= \frac{f^n c^n b^n a^n}{(-c+d)^n (-b+c)^n (-a+b)^n k^{n-1}}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
w_{6n-2} &= \frac{w_{6n-3}z_{6n-5}}{-z_{6n-5} + z_{6n-6}} \\
&= \frac{\frac{f^n c^n b^n a^n}{(-c+d)^n (-b+c)^n (-a+b)^n k^{n-1}} \times \frac{a^n h^n g^{n-1} f^{n-1}}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^{n-1} (f+g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}}{\frac{a^n h^n g^{n-1} f^{n-1}}{(h+k)^n (g+h)^{n-1} (f+g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}} + \frac{a^n h^{n-1} g^{n-1} f^{n-1}}{(h+k)^{n-1} (g+h)^{n-1} (f+g)^{n-1} d^{n-1}}} \\
&= \frac{\frac{f^n c^n b^n a^n h}{(-c+d)^n (-b+c)^n (-a+b)^n k^{n-1} (h+k)}}{\frac{-h}{h+k} + 1} \\
&= \frac{f^n c^n b^n a^n h}{(-c+d)^n (-b+c)^n (-a+b)^n k^n}.
\end{aligned}$$

So, we can prove the other relations and the proof is completed. $\square$

$$5. \text{ ON THE SYSTEM: } z_{n+1} = \frac{z_n w_{n-2}}{w_{n-2} + w_{n-3}}, \quad w_{n+1} = \frac{w_n z_{n-2}}{-z_{n-2} - z_{n-3}}$$

We study in this section the solutions of the system of two difference equations

$$z_{n+1} = \frac{z_n w_{n-2}}{w_{n-2} + w_{n-3}}, \quad w_{n+1} = \frac{w_n z_{n-2}}{-z_{n-2} - z_{n-3}} \quad (5.1)$$

where the initial conditions $z_{-3}, z_{-2}, z_{-1}, z_0, w_{-3}, w_{-2}, w_{-1}, w_0$ are arbitrary non-zero real numbers.

Theorem 4. Assume that $\{z_n, w_n\}_{n=-3}^{\infty}$ is a solution to system (5.1) and let $z_{-3} = d, z_{-2} = c, z_{-1} = b, z_0 = a, w_{-3} = k, w_{-2} = h, w_{-1} = g$ and $w_0 = f$, with $w_{-2} \neq \pm w_{-3}, w_{-1} \neq \pm w_{-2}, w_0 \neq \pm w_{-1}, z_{-2} \neq \pm z_{-3}, z_{-1} \neq \pm z_{-2}$ and $z_0 \neq \pm z_{-1}$. Then, for $n = 0, 1, \dots$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} z_{12n-3} &= \frac{a^{2n} h^{2n} g^{2n} f^{2n}}{(h+k)^{2n}(g+h)^{2n}(f+g)^{2n}d^{2n-1}}, & z_{12n-2} &= \frac{c a^{2n} h^{2n} g^{2n} f^{2n}}{(h+k)^{2n}(g+h)^{2n}(f+g)^{2n}d^{2n}}, \\ z_{12n-1} &= \frac{b a^{2n} h^{2n} g^{2n} f^{2n}}{(h+k)^{2n}(g+h)^{2n}(f+g)^{2n}d^{2n}}, & z_{12n} &= \frac{a^{2n+1} h^{2n} g^{2n} f^{2n}}{(h+k)^{2n}(g+h)^{2n}(f+g)^{2n}d^{2n}}, \\ z_{12n+1} &= \frac{a^{2n+1} h^{2n+1} g^{2n} f^{2n}}{(h+k)^{2n+1}(g+h)^{2n}(f+g)^{2n}d^{2n}}, & z_{12n+2} &= \frac{a^{2n+1} h^{2n+1} g^{2n+1} f^{2n}}{(h+k)^{2n+1}(g+h)^{2n+1}(f+g)^{2n}d^{2n}}, \\ z_{12n+3} &= \frac{a^{2n+1} h^{2n+1} g^{2n+1} f^{2n+1}}{(h+k)^{2n+1}(g+h)^{2n+1}(f+g)^{2n+1}d^{2n+1}}, & z_{12n+4} &= \frac{-c a^{2n+1} h^{2n+1} g^{2n+1} f^{2n+1}}{(h+k)^{2n+1}(g+h)^{2n+1}(f+g)^{2n+1}d^{2n+1}}, \\ z_{12n+5} &= \frac{b a^{2n+1} h^{2n+1} g^{2n+1} f^{2n+1}}{(h+k)^{2n+1}(g+h)^{2n+1}(f+g)^{2n+1}d^{2n+1}}, & z_{12n+6} &= \frac{-a^{2n+2} h^{2n+1} g^{2n+1} f^{2n+1}}{(h+k)^{2n+1}(g+h)^{2n+1}(f+g)^{2n+1}d^{2n+1}}, \\ z_{12n+7} &= \frac{a^{2n+2} h^{2n+2} g^{2n+1} f^{2n+1}}{(h+k)^{2n+2}(g+h)^{2n+1}(f+g)^{2n+1}d^{2n+1}}, & z_{12n+8} &= \frac{-a^{2n+2} h^{2n+2} g^{2n+2} f^{2n+1}}{(h+k)^{2n+2}(g+h)^{2n+2}(f+g)^{2n+1}d^{2n+1}}, \\ w_{12n-3} &= \frac{(-1)^n f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n} a^{2n} h^n g^n}{(c+d)^n(b+c)^n(a+b)^n(2h+k)^n(2g+h)^n(2f+g)^n(c-d)^n(b-c)^n(a-b)^n k^{n-1}}, \\ w_{12n-2} &= \frac{(-1)^n f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n} a^{2n} h^{n+1} g^n}{(c+d)^n(b+c)^n(a+b)^n(2h+k)^n(2g+h)^n(2f+g)^n(c-d)^n(b-c)^n(a-b)^n k^n}, \\ w_{12n-1} &= \frac{(-1)^n f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n} a^{2n} h^n g^{n+1}}{(c+d)^n(b+c)^n(a+b)^n(2h+k)^n(2g+h)^n(2f+g)^n(c-d)^n(b-c)^n(a-b)^n k^n}, \\ w_{12n} &= \frac{(-1)^n f^{2n+1} c^{2n} b^{2n} a^{2n} h^n g^n}{(c+d)^n(b+c)^n(a+b)^n(2h+k)^n(2g+h)^n(2f+g)^n(c-d)^n(b-c)^n(a-b)^n k^n}, \\ w_{12n+1} &= \frac{(-1)^{n+1} f^{2n+1} c^{2n+1} b^{2n} a^{2n} h^n g^n}{(c+d)^{n+1}(b+c)^n(a+b)^n(2h+k)^n(2g+h)^n(2f+g)^n(c-d)^n(b-c)^n(a-b)^n k^n}, \\ w_{12n+2} &= \frac{(-1)^n f^{2n+1} c^{2n+1} b^{2n+1} a^{2n} h^n g^n}{(c+d)^{n+1}(b+c)^{n+1}(a+b)^n(2h+k)^n(2g+h)^n(2f+g)^n(c-d)^n(b-c)^n(a-b)^n k^n}, \end{aligned}$$

$$w_{12n+3} = \frac{(-1)^{n+1} f^{2n+1} c^{2n+1} b^{2n+1} a^{2n+1} h^n g^n}{(c+d)^{n+1} (b+c)^{n+1} (a+b)^{n+1} (2h+k)^n (2g+h)^n (2f+g)^n (c-d)^n (b-c)^n (a-b)^n k^n},$$

$$w_{12n+4} = \frac{(-1)^n f^{2n+1} c^{2n+1} b^{2n+1} a^{2n+1} h^{n+1} g^n}{(c+d)^{n+1} (b+c)^{n+1} (a+b)^{n+1} (2h+k)^{n+1} (2g+h)^n (2f+g)^n (c-d)^n (b-c)^n (a-b)^n k^n},$$

$$w_{12n+5} = \frac{(-1)^{n+1} f^{2n+1} c^{2n+1} b^{2n+1} a^{2n+1} h^{n+1} g^{n+1}}{(c+d)^{n+1} (b+c)^{n+1} (a+b)^{n+1} (2h+k)^{n+1} (2g+h)^{n+1} (2f+g)^n (c-d)^n (b-c)^n (a-b)^n k^n},$$

$$w_{12n+6} = \frac{(-1)^n f^{2n+2} c^{2n+1} b^{2n+1} a^{2n+1} h^{n+1} g^{n+1}}{(c+d)^{n+1} (b+c)^{n+1} (a+b)^{n+1} (2h+k)^{n+1} (2g+h)^{n+1} (2f+g)^{n+1} (c-d)^n (b-c)^n (a-b)^n k^n},$$

$$w_{12n+7} = \frac{(-1)^{n+1} f^{2n+2} c^{2n+2} b^{2n+1} a^{2n+1} h^{n+1} g^{n+1}}{(c+d)^{n+1} (b+c)^{n+1} (a+b)^{n+1} (2h+k)^{n+1} (2g+h)^{n+1} (2f+g)^{n+1} (c-d)^{n+1} (b-c)^n (a-b)^n k^n},$$

$$w_{12n+8} = \frac{(-1)^n f^{2n+2} c^{2n+2} b^{2n+2} a^{2n+1} h^{n+1} g^{n+1}}{(c+d)^{n+1} (b+c)^{n+1} (a+b)^{n+1} (2h+k)^{n+1} (2g+h)^{n+1} (2f+g)^{n+1} (c-d)^{n+1} (b-c)^n (a-b)^n k^n}.$$

Proof. For $n = 0$ the result holds. Now suppose that $n \geq 0$ and that our assumption holds for $n - 1$. That is,

$$z_{12n-15} = \frac{a^{2n-2} h^{2n-2} g^{2n-2} f^{2n-2}}{(h+k)^{2n-2} (g+h)^{2n-2} (f+g)^{2n-2} d^{2n-3}},$$

$$z_{12n-14} = \frac{c a^{2n-2} h^{2n-2} g^{2n-2} f^{2n-2}}{(h+k)^{2n-2} (g+h)^{2n-2} (f+g)^{2n-2} d^{2n-2}},$$

$$z_{12n-13} = \frac{b a^{2n-2} h^{2n-2} g^{2n-2} f^{2n-2}}{(h+k)^{2n-2} (g+h)^{2n-2} (f+g)^{2n-2} d^{2n-2}},$$

$$z_{12n-12} = \frac{a^{2n-1} h^{2n-2} g^{2n-2} f^{2n-2}}{(h+k)^{2n-2} (g+h)^{2n-2} (f+g)^{2n-2} d^{2n-2}},$$

$$z_{12n-11} = \frac{a^{2n-1} h^{2n-1} g^{2n-2} f^{2n-2}}{(h+k)^{2n-1} (g+h)^{2n-2} (f+g)^{2n-2} d^{2n-2}},$$

$$z_{12n-10} = \frac{a^{2n-1} h^{2n-1} g^{2n-1} f^{2n-2}}{(h+k)^{2n-1} (g+h)^{2n-1} (f+g)^{2n-2} d^{2n-2}},$$

$$z_{12n-9} = \frac{a^{2n-1} h^{2n-1} g^{2n-1} f^{2n-1}}{(h+k)^{2n-1} (g+h)^{2n-1} (f+g)^{2n-1} d^{2n-2}},$$

$$z_{12n-8} = \frac{-c a^{2n-1} h^{2n-1} g^{2n-1} f^{2n-1}}{(h+k)^{2n-1} (g+h)^{2n-1} (f+g)^{2n-1} d^{2n-1}},$$

$$z_{12n-7} = \frac{b a^{2n-1} h^{2n-1} g^{2n-1} f^{2n-1}}{(h+k)^{2n-1} (g+h)^{2n-1} (f+g)^{2n-1} d^{2n-1}},$$

$$z_{12n-6} = \frac{-a^{2n} h^{2n-1} g^{2n-1} f^{2n-1}}{(h+k)^{2n-1} (g+h)^{2n-1} (f+g)^{2n-1} d^{2n-1}},$$

$$z_{12n-5} = \frac{a^{2n} h^{2n} g^{2n-1} f^{2n-1}}{(h+k)^{2n} (g+h)^{2n-1} (f+g)^{2n-1} d^{2n-1}},$$

$$z_{12n-4} = \frac{-a^{2n} h^{2n} g^{2n} f^{2n-1}}{(h+k)^{2n} (g+h)^{2n} (f+g)^{2n-1} d^{2n-1}},$$

$$\begin{aligned}
w_{12n-15} &= \frac{(-1)^{n-1} f^{2n-2} c^{2n-2} b^{2n-2} a^{2n-2} h^{n-1} g^{n-1}}{(c+d)^{n-1} (b+c)^{n-1} (a+b)^{n-1} (2h+k)^{n-1} (2g+h)^{n-1} (2f+g)^{n-1} (c-d)^{n-1}}, \\
&\quad (b-c)^{n-1} (a-b)^{n-1} k^{n-2} \\
w_{12n-14} &= \frac{(-1)^{n-1} f^{2n-2} c^{2n-2} b^{2n-2} a^{2n-2} h^n g^{n-1}}{(c+d)^{n-1} (b+c)^{n-1} (a+b)^{n-1} (2h+k)^{n-1} (2g+h)^{n-1} (2f+g)^{n-1} (c-d)^{n-1}}, \\
&\quad (b-c)^{n-1} (a-b)^{n-1} k^{n-1} \\
w_{12n-13} &= \frac{(-1)^{n-1} f^{2n-2} c^{2n-2} b^{2n-2} a^{2n-2} h^{n-1} g^n}{(c+d)^{n-1} (b+c)^{n-1} (a+b)^{n-1} (2h+k)^{n-1} (2g+h)^{n-1} (2f+g)^{n-1} (c-d)^{n-1}}, \\
&\quad (b-c)^{n-1} (a-b)^{n-1} k^{n-1} \\
w_{12n-12} &= \frac{(-1)^{n-1} f^{2n-1} c^{2n-2} b^{2n-2} a^{2n-2} h^{n-1} g^{n-1}}{(c+d)^{n-1} (b+c)^{n-1} (a+b)^{n-1} (2h+k)^{n-1} (2g+h)^{n-1} (2f+g)^{n-1} (c-d)^{n-1}}, \\
&\quad (b-c)^{n-1} (a-b)^{n-1} k^{n-1} \\
w_{12n-11} &= \frac{(-1)^n f^{2n-1} c^{2n-1} b^{2n-2} a^{2n-2} h^{n-1} g^{n-1}}{(c+d)^n (b+c)^{n-1} (a+b)^{n-1} (2h+k)^{n-1} (2g+h)^{n-1} (2f+g)^{n-1} (c-d)^{n-1}}, \\
&\quad (b-c)^{n-1} (a-b)^{n-1} k^{n-1} \\
w_{12n-10} &= \frac{(-1)^{n-1} f^{2n-1} c^{2n-1} b^{2n-1} a^{2n-2} h^{n-1} g^{n-1}}{(c+d)^n (b+c)^n (a+b)^{n-1} (2h+k)^{n-1} (2g+h)^{n-1} (2f+g)^{n-1} (c-d)^{n-1}}, \\
&\quad (b-c)^{n-1} (a-b)^{n-1} k^{n-1} \\
w_{12n-9} &= \frac{(-1)^n f^{2n-1} c^{2n-1} b^{2n-1} a^{2n-1} h^{n-1} g^{n-1}}{(c+d)^n (b+c)^n (a+b)^n (2h+k)^{n-1} (2g+h)^{n-1} (2f+g)^{n-1} (c-d)^{n-1}}, \\
&\quad (b-c)^{n-1} (a-b)^{n-1} k^{n-1} \\
w_{12n-8} &= \frac{(-1)^{n-1} f^{2n-1} c^{2n-1} b^{2n-1} a^{2n-1} h^n g^{n-1}}{(c+d)^n (b+c)^n (a+b)^n (2h+k)^n (2g+h)^{n-1} (2f+g)^{n-1} (c-d)^{n-1}}, \\
&\quad (b-c)^{n-1} (a-b)^{n-1} k^{n-1} \\
w_{12n-7} &= \frac{(-1)^n f^{2n-1} c^{2n-1} b^{2n-1} a^{2n-1} h^n g^n}{(c+d)^n (b+c)^n (a+b)^n (2h+k)^n (2g+h)^n (2f+g)^{n-1} (c-d)^{n-1} (b-c)^{n-1} (a-b)^{n-1} k^{n-1}}, \\
&\quad (-1)^{n-1} f^{2n} c^{2n-1} b^{2n-1} a^{2n-1} h^n g^n \\
w_{12n-6} &= \frac{(-1)^{n-1} f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n-1} a^{2n-1} h^n g^n}{(c+d)^n (b+c)^n (a+b)^n (2h+k)^n (2g+h)^n (2f+g)^n (c-d)^{n-1} (b-c)^{n-1} (a-b)^{n-1} k^{n-1}}, \\
&\quad (-1)^n f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n-1} a^{2n-1} h^n g^n \\
w_{12n-5} &= \frac{(-1)^n f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n} a^{2n-1} h^n g^n}{(c+d)^n (b+c)^n (a+b)^n (2h+k)^n (2g+h)^n (2f+g)^n (c-d)^n (b-c)^{n-1} (a-b)^{n-1} k^{n-1}}, \\
&\quad (-1)^{n-1} f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n} a^{2n-1} h^n g^n \\
w_{12n-4} &= \frac{(-1)^{n-1} f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n} a^{2n-1} h^n g^n}{(c+d)^n (b+c)^n (a+b)^n (2h+k)^n (2g+h)^n (2f+g)^n (c-d)^n (b-c)^n (a-b)^{n-1} k^{n-1}}.
\end{aligned}$$

From system (5.1) we have

$$\begin{aligned}
z_{12n-3} &= \frac{z_{12n-4}w_{12n-6}}{w_{12n-6} + w_{12n-7}} \\
&= \frac{\frac{-a^{2n}h^{2n}g^{2n}f^{2n-1}}{(h+k)^{2n}(g+h)^{2n}(f+g)^{2n-1}d^{2n-1}}}{\frac{(-1)^{n-1}f^{2n}c^{2n-1}b^{2n-1}a^{2n-1}h^ng^n}{(c+d)^n(b+c)^n(a+b)^n(2h+k)^n(2g+h)^n(2f+g)^n(c-d)^{n-1}(b-c)^{n-1}(a-b)^{n-1}k^{n-1}}} \\
&= \frac{\frac{(-1)^{n-1}f^{2n}c^{2n-1}b^{2n-1}a^{2n-1}h^ng^n}{(c+d)^n(b+c)^n(a+b)^n(2h+k)^n(2g+h)^n(2f+g)^n(c-d)^{n-1}(b-c)^{n-1}(a-b)^{n-1}k^{n-1}}}{\frac{(-1)^{n-1}f^{2n}c^{2n-1}b^{2n-1}a^{2n-1}h^ng^n}{(c+d)^n(b+c)^n(a+b)^n(2h+k)^n(2g+h)^n(2f+g)^n(c-d)^{n-1}(b-c)^{n-1}(a-b)^{n-1}k^{n-1}}} \\
&+ \frac{\frac{-a^{2n}h^{2n}g^{2n}f^{2n}}{(h+k)^{2n}(g+h)^{2n}(f+g)^{2n-1}d^{2n-1}(2f+g)}}{\frac{f}{(2f+g)} - 1} \\
&= \frac{a^{2n}h^{2n}g^{2n}f^{2n}}{(h+k)^{2n}(g+h)^{2n}(f+g)^{2n}d^{2n-1}} \\
z_{12n-2} &= \frac{z_{12n-3}w_{12n-5}}{w_{12n-5} + w_{12n-6}} \\
&= \frac{\frac{a^{2n}h^{2n}g^{2n}f^{2n}}{(h+k)^{2n}(g+h)^{2n}(f+g)^{2n}d^{2n-1}}}{\frac{(-1)^nf^{2n}c^{2n}b^{2n-1}a^{2n-1}h^ng^n}{(c+d)^n(b+c)^n(a+b)^n(2h+k)^n(2g+h)^n(2f+g)^n(c-d)^n(b-c)^{n-1}(a-b)^{n-1}k^{n-1}}} \\
&= \frac{\frac{(-1)^nf^{2n}c^{2n}b^{2n-1}a^{2n-1}h^ng^n}{(c+d)^n(b+c)^n(a+b)^n(2h+k)^n(2g+h)^n(2f+g)^n(c-d)^n(b-c)^{n-1}(a-b)^{n-1}k^{n-1}}}{\frac{(-1)^{n-1}f^{2n}c^{2n-1}b^{2n-1}a^{2n-1}h^ng^n}{(c+d)^n(b+c)^n(a+b)^n(2h+k)^n(2g+h)^n(2f+g)^n(c-d)^{n-1}(b-c)^{n-1}(a-b)^{n-1}k^{n-1}}} \\
&+ \frac{\frac{a^{2n}h^{2n}g^{2n}f^{2n}(-c)}{(h+k)^{2n}(g+h)^{2n}(f+g)^{2n}d^{2n-1}(c-d)}}{\frac{-c}{c-d} + 1} \\
&= \frac{a^{2n}h^{2n}g^{2n}f^{2n}c}{(h+k)^{2n}(g+h)^{2n}(f+g)^{2n}d^{2n}} \\
w_{12n-3} &= \frac{w_{12n-4}z_{12n-6}}{-z_{12n-6} - z_{12n-7}} \\
&= \frac{\frac{(-1)^{n-1}f^{2n}c^{2n}b^{2n}a^{2n-1}h^ng^n}{(c+d)^n(b+c)^n(a+b)^n(2h+k)^n(2g+h)^n(2f+g)^n(c-d)^n(b-c)^n(a-b)^{n-1}k^{n-1}}}{\frac{-a^{2n}h^{2n-1}g^{2n-1}f^{2n-1}}{(h+k)^{2n-1}(g+h)^{2n-1}(f+g)^{2n-1}d^{2n-1}} \times \frac{b a^{2n-1}h^{2n-1}g^{2n-1}f^{2n-1}}{(h+k)^{2n-1}(g+h)^{2n-1}(f+g)^{2n-1}d^{2n-1}}} \\
&= \frac{\frac{(-1)^{n-1}f^{2n}c^{2n}b^{2n}a^{2n-1}h^ng^n a}{(c+d)^n(b+c)^n(a+b)^n(2h+k)^n(2g+h)^n(2f+g)^n(c-d)^n(b-c)^n(a-b)^{n-1}k^{n-1}}}{(a-b)} \\
&= \frac{(-1)^nf^{2n}c^{2n}b^{2n}a^{2n}h^ng^n}{(c+d)^n(b+c)^n(a+b)^n(2h+k)^n(2g+h)^n(2f+g)^n(c-d)^n(b-c)^n(a-b)^nk^{n-1}}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 w_{12n-2} &= \frac{w_{12n-3} z_{12n-5}}{-z_{12n-5} - z_{12n-6}} \\
 &= \frac{(-1)^n f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n} a^{2n} h^n g^n}{(c+d)^n (b+c)^n (a+b)^n (2h+k)^n (2g+h)^n (2f+g)^n (c-d)^n (b-c)^n (a-b)^n k^{n-1}} \\
 &\quad \times \frac{a^{2n} h^{2n} g^{2n-1} f^{2n-1}}{(h+k)^{2n} (g+h)^{2n-1} (f+g)^{2n-1} d^{2n-1}} \\
 &= \frac{-a^{2n} h^{2n} g^{2n-1} f^{2n-1}}{(h+k)^{2n} (g+h)^{2n-1} (f+g)^{2n-1} d^{2n-1}} + \frac{a^{2n} h^{2n-1} g^{2n-1} f^{2n-1}}{(h+k)^{2n-1} (g+h)^{2n-1} (f+g)^{2n-1} d^{2n-1}} \\
 &= \frac{(-1)^n f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n} a^{2n} h^n g^n h}{(c+d)^n (b+c)^n (a+b)^n (2h+k)^n (2g+h)^n (2f+g)^n (c-d)^n (b-c)^n (a-b)^n k^{n-1} (h+k)} \\
 &\quad \frac{-h}{h+k} + 1 \\
 &= \frac{(-1)^n f^{2n} c^{2n} b^{2n} a^{2n} h^{n+1} g^n}{(c+d)^n (b+c)^n (a+b)^n (2h+k)^n (2g+h)^n (2f+g)^n (c-d)^n (b-c)^n (a-b)^n k^n}
 \end{aligned}$$

So, we can prove the other relations and the proof is completed.

□

6. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

In order to illustrate the results of the previous sections and to support our theoretical discussions, we present several interesting numerical examples in this section.

Example 1. We take the initial conditions, for the system (2.1), as follows $z_{-3} = 7.5$, $z_{-2} = -12$, $z_{-1} = 9$, $z_0 = 6$, $w_{-3} = 4.75$, $w_{-2} = 24$, $w_{-1} = 13$ and $w_0 = -2$. See Fig. 1.

FIGURE 1

Example 2. We consider numerical example for the difference system (3.1) with the initial conditions $z_{-3} = 5.3, z_{-2} = -.45, z_{-1} = 3.5, z_0 = 11, w_{-3} = 8, w_{-2} = 26, w_{-1} = 14$ and $w_0 = 2$. See Fig. 2.

FIGURE 2

Example 3. See Figure 3. We put the initial condition $z_{-3} = 20, z_{-2} = -3, z_{-1} = 9, z_0 = 6, w_{-3} = 4.75, w_{-2} = 24, w_{-1} = 13$ and $w_0 = 18$ on the difference system (4.1)

FIGURE 3

Example 4. Fig. 4 shows the behavior of the solution of the difference system (5.1) with the initial conditions $z_{-3} = 24, z_{-2} = -30, z_{-1} = 11, z_0 = -5.5, w_{-3} = 7, w_{-2} = 13, w_{-1} = 8.75$ and $w_0 = -14$.

FIGURE 4

CONCLUSION

This paper discussed the expression's form of systems of rational Fourth order difference equations. In Section 2, we obtained the form of the solutions of system $z_{n+1} = \frac{z_n w_{n-2}}{w_{n-2} + w_{n-3}}$, $w_{n+1} = \frac{w_n z_{n-2}}{z_{n-2} + z_{n-3}}$. Also In section 3, we found the solution's form of the system $z_{n+1} = \frac{z_n w_{n-2}}{w_{n-2} + w_{n-3}}$, $w_{n+1} = \frac{w_n z_{n-2}}{z_{n-2} - z_{n-3}}$. In section 4,5 , we got the solution of the following systems respectively, $z_{n+1} = \frac{z_n w_{n-2}}{w_{n-2} + w_{n-3}}$, $w_{n+1} = \frac{w_n z_{n-2}}{-z_{n-2} + z_{n-3}}$ and $z_{n+1} = \frac{z_n w_{n-2}}{w_{n-2} + w_{n-3}}$, $w_{n+1} = \frac{w_n z_{n-2}}{-z_{n-2} - z_{n-3}}$. Finally, we gave a numerical example in each case to illustrates the results.

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